

Japanese Figures in the Video Game Industry: Hideo Kojima (III)

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Hello again, readers. I am finally able to present the third and final article dedicated to Hideo Kojima, in which we will continue the story from the games following *Metal Gear Solid 4: Guns of the Patriots*, and discuss his most recent projects to date, following the controversy surrounding his departure from Konami under unusual circumstances. Readers should be aware that major plot elements from various video games will be revealed throughout this text.

The end of Big Boss's story and Kojima's farewell to Konami

Solid Snake's story concluded in *Guns of the Patriots*, but Hideo Kojima still felt the need to tell the events that occurred between *Metal Gear Solid 3: Snake Eater* and *Metal Gear*. This was explored through the PSP games *Metal Gear Solid: Portable Ops* (2006) and *Metal Gear Solid: Peace Walker* (2010), the latter later adapted for home consoles. In 2010, the Spanish game *Castlevania: Lords of Shadow* was also released, a reinterpretation of the *Castlevania* series by the Madrid-based studio MercurySteam, produced by Kojima, who suggested various design details, including the appearance of the protagonist, Gabriel Belmont.

In *Portable Ops* and *Peace Walker*, the story focuses on Big Boss creating his own mercenary army after the events of *Snake Eater*. Kojima's involvement in *Portable Ops* was limited to production, but he was directly involved in the development of *Peace Walker*, a title allowing multiple players to join the battle cooperatively, emphasizing the army aspect rather than the action of a single man. Big Boss must confront his past and his relationship with The Boss, as he never truly "let her go," feeling that she was unfair by not explaining why she deserted and why she did not trust him with her secret.

The story begins when Snake accepts a mission proposed by his second-in-command, Kazuhira Miller—who would later support Solid and be killed by Liquid—. A supposed professor, Ramón Gálvez, and a student from the University of Peace in Costa Rica request his help to investigate a mysterious military force deployed in the region. Snake hesitates but accepts upon hearing The Boss's voice on a cassette carried by Paz Ortega, Gálvez's student.

During the mission, Snake discovers that The Boss's voice came from Dr. Strangelove—named after the film *Dr. Strangelove* (1964)— attempting to replicate The Boss's personality in an artificial intelligence, designed to be installed in a massive armoured vehicle called Peace Walker, capable of responding to nuclear attacks. Snake realizes that he shares Strangelove's obsession with his mentor, who did not return the scientist's feelings.

Characters such as Dr. Huey Emmerich—Otacon's father and future husband of Strangelove— develop the first Metal Gears, attempting to grant the armoured vehicles the ability to walk, since he himself could not walk due to his disability. Peace Walker was being developed under the orders of Coldman, a CIA agent who intended to show that humans were unfit to decide on nuclear retaliation, trusting the responsibility to AI. Seeing the danger, Snake summons his private army to stop Coldman, destroying Peace Walker and other experimental weapons from the team.

Snake faces a set of weapons controlled by artificial intelligences and collects their components to build his first Metal Gear, the bipedal tank Zeke, which is later hijacked by Paz, who reveals herself to be an agent of the Patriots recently formed by Major Zero—then known as Cipher. Ramón Gálvez, in reality a KGB agent named Vladimir Zadornov, plans to hack Peace Walker for the Soviet Union, and Paz helps him escape to distract Snake while he seizes control of the weapon.

Snake with Gálvez (Zadornov) and Paz; on the right, Miller. This image belongs to an animated sequence from the video game *Metal Gear Solid: Peace Walker*. These sequences were created by animating illustrations by artists Ashley Wood and Yōji Shinkawa.

Boss defeats Paz and she disappears, while Zadornov ultimately dies when Snake defends himself against him in combat. Paz, together with Chico —the nickname of Ricardo Valenciano Libre—, is one of the two characters who once again introduce the theme of child soldiers to the audience. Chico is a young militiaman of the Nicaraguan Sandinista National Liberation Army, fighting alongside his sister Amanda. Paz —whose real name is later revealed to be Pacifica Ocean— would eventually be exposed as, in fact, an adult woman with a youthful appearance, and an agent sent by Zero in an attempt to persuade Snake to rejoin him.

Snake would continue to follow his own interpretation of the world envisioned by his mentor: the creation of a world in which soldiers would follow nothing but their own ideals, free from the control of any state. Zero, on the other hand, held a different vision of peace —one of total control, where the absence of freedom and the presence of censorship would prevent people from having to think for themselves, allowing them to live under a false image of peace and happiness.

The Metal Gear series received a new instalment, this time with a completely different theme and approach, with *Metal Gear Rising: Revengeance*. The game stars Raiden and was initially planned to be developed by Kojima Productions —under the title *Metal Gear Solid: Rising*— and was meant to depict the events taking place between *Metal Gear Solid 2* and *Metal Gear Solid 4*. It would have told the story of Raiden’s mission to rescue Olga Gurlukovich’s baby, Sunny.

The project was eventually cancelled, but development was transferred to the studio PlatinumGames, founded by developers such as Atsushi Inaba and Hideki Kamiya —known for Capcom titles like *Viewtiful Joe* and *Devil May Cry*—, a studio also responsible for franchises such as Bayonetta and the video game *NieR: Automata*.

The project was reborn as *Metal Gear Rising: Revengeance*, a hack-and-slash game in which players control Raiden in events set after *Metal Gear Solid 4: Guns of the Patriots*, following Snake’s disappearance and the proliferation of private military companies and cybernetic bodies.

In *Metal Gear Rising: Revengeance*, Raiden confronts enemies such as Samuel Rodrigues —Jetstream Sam—, a member of a private military force.

Big Boss's story concludes in the final video game developed by Hideo Kojima for Konami, *Metal Gear Solid V*, which was divided into two instalments: *Ground Zeroes* (2014) and *The Phantom Pain* (2015). Both games reintroduce the character and base-management system for Snake and the soldiers stationed at his headquarters—and in *The Phantom Pain* players can also visit the base where Snake's army resides—while incorporating gameplay mechanics typical of open-world games.

One year after the events of *Peace Walker*, Snake learns that Paz is still alive and has been captured, along with Chico, by Cipher—the Patriots—and that both are being held in a secret prison camp known as Camp Omega, operated by the United States government.

After infiltrating Camp Omega, Snake rescues Chico and Paz, but soon becomes the victim of a surprise attack on his base orchestrated by a new character, Skull Face, and his personal unit, XOF. Dozens of his soldiers, both men and women, are killed in the assault. Snake himself is injured when his helicopter crashes due to a bomb that had been placed in Paz's uterus—another device located in her abdomen had been removed shortly before. Kaz, Snake's second-in-command, is also severely wounded during the attack.

Naked Snake and Kaz after the attack on their base

The Phantom Pain continues the events of *Ground Zeroes*, nine years after what was depicted in that game. The player witnesses Big Boss awakening in a hospital after nine years in a coma, having lost an arm and with shrapnel embedded in his body as a result of the accident. Snake rises from his bed with the help of a mysterious character, Ishmael, who saves his life from an attempt on it by an assassin—later revealed to be Quiet—. The player witnesses how this woman kills the surgeon and nursing staff in cold blood, also attacking Ishmael.

The protagonist attempts to escape from the hospital with Ishmael's help, and later with Ocelot's, after Ishmael and the protagonist suffer a road accident while fleeing their pursuers: members of the XOF forces under the command of Skull Face, as well as a mysterious character, The Man on Fire—who will later be revealed to be none other than the body of Colonel Volgin, the main antagonist of *Metal Gear Solid 3: Snake Eater*, reanimated through the psychic powers of the Third Child and the rage he still harboured toward Big Boss—.

The script of this video game is presented to the audience in an episodic format, similar to that of a television series, and makes extensive use of many different types of camera shots, including numerous long takes, showcasing Kojima and his team's knowledge of cinema. Across two large scenarios, players gradually uncover the main plot of the game, after their first mission sends them to rescue Kazuhira Miller, who has been captured in Afghanistan.

It is a video game centred on revenge, both on the part of the protagonist and of those around him, with constant references to Herman Melville's novel *Moby-Dick*.

Snake and Ishmael watch, helpless and astonished, during their escape from the hospital as XOF forces execute civilians in cold blood while searching for Snake.

Revenge is also the primary motive driving the antagonist of this adventure, Skull Face, who turns out to be a former member of FOX and harbours resentment against the military for devastating his homeland and imposing another language upon him, making him forget his identity and origins.

In FOX, Skull Face was responsible for providing covert support to Naked Snake and other operatives during their missions, remaining in the shadows while Naked Snake and Major Zero received credit for averting the potential catastrophe triggered by Volgin and The Boss in *Snake Eater*.

Skull Face also resents Zero's vision of uniting the world under Western American culture and the English language, which he considers degrading to all other societies on Earth. To execute his revenge, Skull Face enlists the cooperation of Dr. Huey Emmerich, an expert in bipedal weapons and former colleague of Big Boss —later revealed to be partly responsible for allowing Skull Face's assault on Snake and his comrades' base.

The bipedal weapon Sahelanthropus, developed by Emmerich, becomes Skull Face's tool to convince all nations of the utility of nuclear warheads against each other, while also planning to make them available to anyone, thereby breaking the overwhelming power that the United States holds over the world.

His master plan involves eradicating all English speakers using mysterious parasites studied by another new character, Dr. Code Talker, a Diné (Navajo) native forced to collaborate with Skull Face and later rescued by Big Boss. Quiet, the assassin, worked for Skull Face's XOF organization, failing in her attempt to kill Big Boss in the hospital and being burned by Ishmael.

She was treated using parasites that Code Talker applied to himself, granting her regenerative powers that allow her to survive, abilities based on those of the sniper *The End*, who could even restore his health through photosynthesis in *Snake Eater* —one of the superhuman capabilities that typically characterize Snake's various enemies, such as Vamp's near immortality due to his nanomachines.

Quiet reveals to Code Talker that she is not mute, using Navajo, a language she knows, to inform the scientist about the strain of the parasite infecting her: the English strain. In the image, she tells the doctor that she has not used that language since being infected.

Quiet is also infected by a parasite that activates in the host when it detects a specific language. Skull Face has been conducting terrible experiments on civilian populations in Africa with the parasite, developing in Quiet a strain that targets English speakers. Believing that languages shape the world and bind human beings, he plans to eradicate languages like English from the face of the Earth in the most drastic way: by eliminating their speakers. Quiet, hence her name —“silent”— refuses to speak English, earning her nickname.

The sniper will end up being distrusted by many of Snake's comrades, as they come from XOF even though she has proven herself completely loyal to Big Boss, and she will even be humiliated, tortured, and mistreated by her own team, either for no apparent reason or to extract information.

The Phantom Pain is filled with very harsh moments and gruesome scenes, whose impact is felt even more by the player, as they are directly responsible for actions such as purging an entire group of their own soldiers —recruited by the player throughout the game and deployable on missions— infected with the parasite.

Given the multiracial composition of Snake's army, and the fact that his men and women speak different languages, it becomes the player's task to discover which language triggers the plague in their ranks, by quarantining all speakers of a given language and determining if it is the activator of the strain —this is not done automatically, but manually by the player, making them directly responsible for the deaths of soldiers who perish if a wrong decision is made—.

Big Boss falls to his knees, overcome by the anguish and rage he feels for having to kill his own soldiers in cold blood—an act the player must carry out to progress in the game's story—. In this scene, he is depicted allegorically with the shrapnel lodged in his head forming a horn and covered in blood.

All of this occurs after the death of the main villain of this instalment, Skull Face, with the game drawing on the concept of *phantom pain* that gives the title its meaning, in which an absent element or character indirectly causes an effect.

Snake and his allies ultimately take down Skull Face in a close-range final shootout, in which he, Miller, and later Emmerich, fire wildly at Skull Face with his own shotgun. Momentarily, past versions of Snake and Miller appear during the destruction of Mother Base nine years earlier, as if their own ghosts from the past were taking revenge on the villain. However, Skull Face had already set part of his plan in motion, directly or indirectly, by infecting Huey and Snake's men with a parasite to weaken their ranks, and by sending Quiet, who had been inoculated with the parasite linked to the English language — which she refused to activate.

The issue of child soldiers also appears in this game, led by a boy named Eli, who is clearly a young Liquid Snake, commanding a group of child mercenaries that Snake eventually accepts into his base. Among them are several children forced to work in diamond mines in Central Africa. One of Snake's contacts orders him to kill these children, but Snake refuses, faking a shooting —recording a false gunfire audio— before taking them to his base.

Eli is a tortured soul, scarred by the aggression he has witnessed, feeling weak whenever Snake, Ocelot, or his men treat him with either condescension or affection in an attempt to curb his violent behaviour. Instead of adapting, he ends up fleeing the base, taking with him the Sahelanthropus, a new bipedal vehicle developed by Emmerich for Skull Face, which Snake and his men had recovered for their own use.

Among Eli's child followers is also Tretij Rebenok —Russian for “the Third Child”— none other than a young Psycho Mantis, the adversary of Solid Snake in *Metal Gear Solid* (which occurs years after *Metal Gear Solid V*), whose psychic powers were being exploited by XOF, and who escapes with Eli, beginning his cooperation with the future Liquid Snake.

Ocelot —left— and Snake —right— watch as the child soldiers hijack a helicopter under Eli's orders, escaping from Mother Base and also stealing the bipedal armored vehicle Sahelanthropus.

But this is not the end of the game, as more surprises still await the players. Emmerich is not only responsible for allowing XOF to destroy Snake's base nine years earlier and infect his soldiers, but he also murdered his wife and Otacon's mother, Dr. Strangelove, locking her inside the Peace Walker AI capsule to die of asphyxiation. The AI had been programmed based on The Boss's personality and was later rescued after the events of Peace Walker by Strangelove herself.

Snake decides to exile Huey in a scene where almost all of his men and officers shout in unison for his execution. Years later, the scientist would take his own life after discovering that his son, Otacon, had a relationship with his second wife —something Otacon never revealed to his half-sister Emma to avoid hurting her.

Meanwhile, Quiet flees Mother Base without explanation to avoid putting Snake in danger. She is eventually captured by a military contingent whose soldiers attempt to assault her. She manages to escape, killing several guards in the process, and Snake arrives just as she succeeds, aiding the sniper during her escape. Both are surrounded by a convoy of heavily armed Soviet armoured vehicles.

They destroy several of the vehicles, but Quiet eventually falls unconscious from her wounds, forcing Snake —also injured— to hide with her in the desert near the area where she had been held captive. Boss is bitten by a venomous snake while they are hiding from their enemies. Terrified and fearing for Snake's life, Quiet uses English to call one of Mother Base's helicopters, giving away her position.

By doing so, she knows she is putting her life at risk and that the parasite will activate. After the helicopter arrives and rescues Snake, she decides to leave him forever, demonstrating unwavering loyalty to him and giving Quiet a charisma that contrasts with the controversial design of the character.

Snake himself will not know the reason for her sacrifice, as she pretends she cannot speak, until the moment Quiet leaves him. Code Talker is the first to truly understand why Quiet stopped speaking, alongside the players themselves.

Quiet, after abandoning Snake

The most significant surprise in the story of this video game is revealed in the true ending of the title. Although Hideo Kojima had left several hints throughout the game, he still caught franchise fans off guard by revealing that, throughout the game, we had not been controlling the real Big Boss, but his ghost, his shadow, a double.

Once this fact is known, many visual and auditory easter eggs and hidden messages throughout the narrative development of the game become understandable.

In the trailer for *The Phantom Pain*, shown years before the game's release, and whose image we have shown on previous pages, with Snake and Miller on a stretcher, a perspective is presented indicating that the camera represents the viewpoint of another character who is observing them. Upon unlocking a special mission called "Truth: The Man Who Sold the World," players will see sequences previously viewed, but altered, showing what really happened. This includes the hospital scene, where Miller asks about Snake's condition, but adding at the end of the same scene the phrase, "What about him?" while turning his gaze toward the player.

In the prologue sequence of *The Phantom Pain*, in which Snake must escape a hospital in Cyprus with the help of Ishmael—who, at the end of this version of the sequence, is finally revealed to be the real Big Boss—hints are given as David Bowie's song *The Man Who Sold the World* plays in the room. The song speaks of a man encountering his double.

The protagonist undergoes cosmetic surgery to prevent enemies from finding him, with his original appearance generated by the player. This is the true appearance of Snake's double, who is revealed to have been the doctor who operated on Paz in an attempt to save her from the bombs that had been planted inside her body, failing to remove the second one in time. After the explosion, he placed himself in front of Snake to take the brunt of the blast during the attack on Mother Base in *Ground Zeroes*.

Moment in which Miller—centre, wearing sunglasses—addresses the player, asking the doctors about the condition of the other character, later revealed to be the protagonist of *The Phantom Pain*. The camera moves in a way that indicates it represents the viewpoint of this other character, who is none other than Venom Snake, the Big Boss of this game.

This explains events such as why Big Boss never appeared with a prosthetic arm as an elderly man in chronologically later games, and why he did not have the piece of shrapnel lodged in his head shown in this game.

Moreover, characters like Emmerich comment that they do not recognize Snake in certain actions, such as approving torture. The AI based on The Boss, programmed to recognize Big Boss, also reacts strangely to this Snake—called Venom Snake or Ahab, like the captain in *Moby Dick*—telling him that he is not Jack, the name by which Naked Snake is also known and the one The Boss used to refer to him.

During the story, Eli calls Venom Snake “father” on multiple occasions. Venom himself is aware of the *Les Enfants Terribles* project, by which the original Big Boss was cloned without permission. As Venom retains part of the real Snake’s memories, he follows Ocelot’s advice to perform DNA tests on Eli, which reveal that the boy has no genetic relation to him. This also makes the player suspicious, since all signs point to Eli undoubtedly being Liquid, the son and clone of Big Boss.

It all turns out to be a scheme by Major Zero to hide Snake, later exploited by the real Naked Snake, who in this game is shown again as a more morally complex character than Kojima made him appear in the fourth instalment when reuniting with Solid. Big Boss has proven to be a man who, for his ideals, sacrificed everything, even destroying the true identity of one of his best men, to take revenge on Zero and build his mercenary nation.

Snake has been able to use one of his soldiers as a puppet, and through hypnosis practiced by Ocelot and cosmetic surgery, make him assume the persona and burden of the real Big Boss, causing enemy attacks to be directed at him while the real Big Boss hides to prepare Outer Heaven and also build the Zanzibar Land fortress, where years later—and the player, years earlier—Solid Snake will face him in *Metal Gear 2: Solid Snake* (1990).

Venom, meanwhile, will be the Big Boss that Solid faces in Outer Heaven during the events of the original *Metal Gear* (1987), thus explaining, almost thirty years later, how Big Boss seemingly dies twice. Big Boss left a cassette for Venom, called “Operation Intrude N313,” which turns out to be the mission name given to Solid Snake to stop him, closing the narrative circle of the saga and connecting it to the events of the earliest games in the franchise.

This plot twist recalls that taken by Akira Kurosawa in the film *Kagemusha* (1980), although in that film it is clear that the Takeda Shingen we see throughout most of the movie is the “shadow,” the double who assumes his personality to protect the famous daimyō (Japanese feudal lord). In Japanese, the term *kagemusha*—“shadow warrior”—refers to a political decoy. It is exactly the same technique Snake uses in *The Phantom Pain* against his enemies.

In the film, the thief who becomes Takeda Shingen’s double begins to adopt traits of Takeda himself, showing honour, great military skills, and truly becoming a shadow or ghost of the leader he represents, just as will happen with Venom Snake. As Naked Snake himself reveals to Venom on the mentioned cassette, alongside him, both are Big Boss.

Along with a *Ground Zeroes* mission in which players retraced various scenes from *Metal Gear Solid* and collected logos and titles from the series, this is Kojima's farewell to the users, breaking the fourth wall several times during this final mission. For example, Ocelot hands a passport with a new identity to the real Snake, which displays the username and the month and day of birth entered by the player at the start of the game, implying that the player is now Big Boss.

This mirrors the end of *Metal Gear Solid 2*, when Raiden sees the dog tag names given by Solid Snake, displaying the name and some details entered by the player. The cassette recording represents the real Big Boss, breaking the fourth wall again. While simultaneously speaking to his double, he thanks Venom [the player] for accompanying him and also says that both of them are Big Boss, to which Venom responds by breaking the mirror in front of him, smiling at the player.

The puppet double charade was so strictly followed by Hideo Kojima that a phantom studio called *Moby Dick Studio* was created, led by a certain Joakim Mogren, who turned out to be a fictional character using Ishmael's bandages to hide, and later revealed to be part of a marketing strategy, creating a fake studio to conceal the development of *The Phantom Pain*.

Kojima himself appeared with a Mogren mask that incorporated bandages, to reveal the truth moments later.

Scene from the true ending of *Metal Gear Solid V: The Phantom Pain*, in which the real Snake prepares to depart after having organised his escape and identity swap with Ocelot, who now goes to meet the double, Venom Snake. This explains Ishmael's sudden absence after the accident. Venom lost consciousness during the hospital escape, and Ocelot removed Big Boss from there, leaving Venom alone, only to later return to him and then begin the main storyline of the game. Another clue that led fans to suspect something was off with the protagonist is that part of this same scene appeared in game trailers, showing Snake on the same outfit, riding his motorcycle, but with Venom's prosthetic arm and the shrapnel lodged in his skull—a scene that never made it into the final game.

Kojima today

After leaving Konami, a project Kojima Productions was developing was cancelled: the video game *P.T. Silent Hills*, which was being created in collaboration with film director Guillermo del Toro. This game even had a free downloadable demo on PlayStation 4 in 2014. It was intended to be a future survival horror game, in the style of the classic *Resident Evil* and *Silent Hill*. After leaving Konami, Kojima re-founded his studio, Kojima Productions, and developed *Death Stranding*, which was announced in 2016 and released in 2019.

It revolves around death and the battlefield and features actors such as Norman Reedus —famous for his role as Daryl Dixon in *The Walking Dead* series— and Mads Mikkelsen —well known for roles such as Dr. Hannibal Lecter in the series *Hannibal* or LeChiffre in the James Bond saga—, including a character played by the famous director Guillermo del Toro, who had been collaborating with Kojima on *P.T.* until he left Konami, and who maintains a good relationship with the Japanese creator.

Konami, for its part, announced the game *Metal Gear Survive*, loosely based on the Metal Gear franchise —released in 2018—, and, like other titles, it used the Fox Engine developed by Kojima’s team, which was also employed in the pachinko machine remake of *Metal Gear Solid 3: Snake Eater*. Since Konami took control of the Fox Engine —whose lead programmer was among the first to be fired after Kojima’s departure—, Kojima Productions chose the Decima engine for *Death Stranding*, which had been used by Guerrilla Games in titles such as *Horizon Zero Dawn* (2016).

Appearance of director Guillermo del Toro in the 2016 *Death Stranding* trailer at The Game Awards

Since its release in 2019, *Death Stranding* has established itself as one of the most unique works in Hideo Kojima’s career. Far from offering a conventional experience, the game proposes a reflection on loneliness, loss, death, and the need to rebuild human connections in a fragmented world.

Its gameplay system, based on indirect cooperation between players —the so-called “strand system”— transforms interaction into an act of anonymous help, reinforcing the idea of community in contrast to isolation.

In this sense, Kojima translates into gameplay a metaphor about human interdependence, with a positive vision that proposes solutions to the epidemic of loneliness that humanity has been experiencing. Curiously, the game was released shortly before the COVID-19 pandemic, which forced people in the real world into a situation similar to that of the characters in this adventure.

Although *Death Stranding* marked a formal departure from Metal Gear, many of Kojima's creative obsessions remain intact. The use of the body as a battlefield and a weapon—not only the limbs, but also blood, used as ammunition in various weapons employed by the protagonist Sam Porter Bridges—, the constant presence of traumatic memory, the critique of control systems, and the manipulation of language and information continue to be central elements of his discourse. Likewise, the work delves into a fragmented and symbolic narrative that requires active player engagement, reaffirming Kojima as an author interested in exploring the expressive limits of video games as a cultural medium beyond mere entertainment.

Currently, Kojima continues to develop projects from a position of unprecedented creative independence in his career. With the release of *Death Stranding 2: On the Beach*, the author has confirmed that his new narrative universe was not an isolated experiment but the beginning of a coherent and extended creative stage. The sequel deepens the issues posed in the first game—the fragility of human bonds, reconstruction after catastrophe, and technological interdependence— consolidating the “strand system” as one of the most original contributions to contemporary game design.

Since leaving Konami and refounding Kojima Productions, Kojima has established himself as a fully autonomous creative figure, capable of operating at the intersection of video games, cinema, and contemporary cultural reflection. Far from representing an epilogue, this stage constitutes an expansion of his creative identity.

Sources

- **Texts consulted:** Domenech Alcaide, A. (2017), *Los videojuegos como producto del arte: La influencia e importancia del dibujo, del cómic y otras artes en su historia* (Doctoral thesis), University of Granada; *Metal Gear Solid: El legado de Big Boss*; *Metal Gear Informer*; Kojima Productions; Konami; IGN | **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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